

Starved Flatworm VS Fed Flatworm Time to Find Food and Behavior Throughout the Time Period

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Abstract. Flatworms come under the phylum Platyhelminthes with the diversity of 12,821 species. I collected the marine water flatworm *Paucumara* sp. from a lab culture and performed a flatworm feeding experiment, using starved and fed flatworm to discover how long it takes for the flatworms to find food, and their feeding behavior. I found that the starved flatworms are mostly eager to search and look for food while fed flatworm tend to just ignore the food and wander around at a random path. My results suggested that the fed flatworms were not eager to find food while the starved one were more eager, which is the general behavior of animals.

1. Introduction

Flatworms, or platyhelminth, are carnivorous that feed on other animals. They exist in both fresh and salt water. Over 80% of flatworm are parasitic (living of another organism), and the other 20% are free living species ^[1]. Planarian flatworms have a head segment that contains concentrated sensory organs and nervous tissue (brain), which can be used to locate food, response, and signal movement. The receptors responsible for feeding behavior are scattered along the margin of the worm. It requires the stimulation of two sets of receptors to locate food. The lateral (sideways) receptors are necessary for turning, and the anterior (head) receptors are necessary to send signals to direct and convey food into the mouth. When food is presented at the lateral portion where the eyes are located, the feeding behavior is much more vigorous and prompt ^[2]. Overall, the inhibition of feeding is dependent on the coordination of nervous system that link sensory signal, the CNS (central nervous system) and the motor organs to trigger behavioral responses. Koopowitz and colleagues found that when the margin of the flatworm has been cut, the flatworm were unable to sense the food, and they concluded that hungry animals will respond to external stimulus such as vibrations in the water near them ^[2]. The paper mentioned above only talks about the sensory aspects of feeding, however there is no mentioning about whether flatworms will ignore food offered if they are fully fed or what will hungry flatworms do to find food. In this experiment, I will endeavor to analyze and perform experiments on how starved and fed flatworms react to food and their behavior.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Preparation Of Starved And Fed Flatworm Specimens

The specimens of marine flatworm species *Paucumara* sp. were acquired from a lab culture. The flatworms were divided into two different batches and were then transferred to two different containers containing 19ppt salinity water with the temperature of 27.9 degrees Celsius. Flatworms in one of the containers were starved for three days while the others were fed with 0.5g of pig liver homogenate daily.

2.2. Flatworm Feeding Experiments Setting

A small piece of homogenized pig liver was placed in the middle of the dish. The starved and fed flatworms were then placed on the opposite side of the dish using a pipette. The movement of the flatworms were then recorded with the recording device prepared to observe its behavior and its path throughout the experiment. The experiments were repeated, and the results were recorded in videos using a camera (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Picture of Camera used throughout the experiment (model: iPad Pro)

2.3. Feeding Eagerness Analysis - Ratio Of Flatworm Distance To The Food Source At The End (E) To Distance To The Food Source At The Beginning (B)

After the experiment, the video data was used to analyze the movement of the two different types of flatworms (starved versus fed). During this period, two screenshots of the video were taken, one at the beginning and the other one at the end of each experiment. The screenshot taken at the beginning was labeled as screenshot 1 and the screenshot that was taken at the end was labeled as screenshot 2. A map that shows the movement of the flatworm specimen was then drawn on the screenshots 2, the one taken at the end. To track and draw the map, I used my recording device and an iPad Pro. I was watching the record video while drawing the map on the screenshots at the end of the experiment. The map illustrated the route that the flatworm took in the process of finding food. The distance of the route was measured using a string to lay on the movement track on the screenshot and a ruler to measure the length. The distance between the flatworm and the food source at the beginning was assigned as B and began the distance to the food source at the end was assigned as E. When E/B is large and closer to 1, the less movement the flatworm made and less eager was the flatworm to find food; when E/B is closer to 0, the more movement the flatworm made toward food source and more eager was the flatworm to forage.

2.4. Movement Trail Analysis - Path Distance Travel (D) To Displacement (d) Analysis

To analyze the flatworms' behavior and movement, the distance travelled by the flatworm (D) and the overall displacement of the flatworm specimen (d) was labeled along with different phases. Displacement (d) was defined as the distance between the starting and ending point of the movement trail of the flatworm. Distance travelled (D) was defined by the total distance travelled between the beginning and the end point. To outline the distance and a ruler was used to measure the string, while the displacement was measured directly with the ruler. The value of distance over displacement was then computed.

3. Results

Our results show that starved flatworms were mostly attracted to the food. The full flatworm didn't respond to the bait which is genuinely reasonable, since they were already full and didn't need it. We performed a feeding eagerness analysis the ratio E/B and a movement track analysis of distance travelled to displacement (D/d) to analyze the foraging movement of starved and fed flatworms. The results were summarized in Table 1.

	E/B			D/d			
	E	B	E/B	Phases	D	d	D/d
Starved flatworm (experiment 1)	0	9	0	1	22	10	2.2
				2	N/A		
				3	1	1	1
Fed flatworm (experiment 1)		9	9	1	N/A		
Starved flatworm (experiment 2)	0	6	0	1 (part 1)	7.4	10.5	7.04
				1 (part 2)	9	3.5	2.57
				2 (part 1)	6	1	6
				2 (part 2)	5	1	5
				3	1	1	1
Fed flatworm (experiment 2)		6	6	1	N/A		

Table 1: Shows the E/B value for both fed and starved flatworms in experiment 1 and 2.

Shows the D/d value for the starved flatworms in both experiments. Measure exchange: 1cm in real life equals to 2.91cm on Figures 2 and 3.

3.1. Feeding Eagerness Analysis – Ratio Of Distance To The Food Source At The End (E) To That At The Beginning (B)

The starved flatworm wandered around the edge of the petri dish and moved around the petri dish to locate the pig liver. In the first experiment (Fig. 2), the starved flatworms moved around the edge of the petri dish (as seen in the video) from 0:00 to 5:57. Then the flatworm moved in a zigzag from 5:57 to 6:35. Then the flatworm moved in a curved line till 6:55 and finally moved in a straight line toward the food source till 7:04, when it finally reached the food (the pig liver) and marked the end of the experiment. On the other hand, during the experiment, the fed flatworm moved 5 mm (according to the screenshot) along the edge of the petri dish from 0:00 to 2:29 and did not move from 2:29 to the end of the video. Figure 2A shown the location of the flatworm at 0:00 while Fig. 2B shown the flatworm at 7:04 (the end of the experiment) as well as the movement track map. The distance of the starved flatworm to the food source at the beginning of the experiment was 9cm while that at the end (E) was 0cm. Hence, the ratio of E to B (E/B) equals to 0, meaning the starved flatworm had reached the food. On the other hand, the distance of the fed flatworm from the food source at the beginning and at the end were both 9cm, so the ratio of E to B equals to 1, meaning the fed flatworm didn't move at all (values shown in Table 1).

In the second experiment (Fig. 3), the starved flatworm moved in a straight line from 0:00 to 00:15. Then the flatworm made a turn to the edge of the petri dish and circled around the dish till 2:15. Then from here the flatworm made a semi loop from 2:15 to 2:25. The flatworm then moved in a straight line till 2:97 and began to move in a circle along the petri dish again till 3:86. In this time period the flatworm sensed (noticed) the vague location of the pig liver and began to move around this area till 6:29. The flatworm then moved in two semi circles, to the place where the flatworm began the final phase, which was from where the flatworm noticed the accurate spot and only took 10 seconds to reach the pig liver. The distance of the starved flatworm to the food source at the beginning of the experiment (B) was 6cm while that at the end (E) was 0cm. Hence, the ratio of E to B (E/B) equal to 0, meaning the starved flatworm had reached the food. On the other hand, the distance of the fed flatworm from the food source at the beginning and at the end were both 6cm, so the ratio of E to B equal to 1, meaning the fed flatworm didn't move at all (Values shown in Table 1).

3.2. Movement Trail Analysis - Ratios Of Distance Travel (D) To Displacement (d)

The bigger distance over displacement the more time it's needed for the flatworms to arrive at the destination, which was, in this study, the food source. In the first experiment, the D/d value of the starved flatworms in the phases 1 was 2.2cm. On the other hand, the D/d value of the starved flatworms in phase 3 was 1cm. We define that, when the value of D/d over or equals 2, the flatworm was in the first phase. As for phase 3 the final phase, we defined the flatworm enter this phase when the D/d value was near or equal to 1. Hence, the D/d value of starved flatworms in phase 1 was more than that of the starved flatworms in phase 3, indicating that in phases 1 was the wandering phase since the value was over 2 while the third phase was a straight approach when D/d was near or equally to the number one (Values seen in Table 1).

In the second experiment, the ratio of D to d in the first phase was 7.04. On the other hand, phase 2 gave the D/d value of 6. As for phase 1 part two, it gave the D/d value of 2.57. The flatworm then moves to the next phase, phase 2 part two and gave the D/d value of 5. Phase 3 illustrated a straight line when the flatworm approached the food, meaning that D and d were the same and the D/d value was 1. Thus, we defined when the value of D/d was over or equal to 2 as the first phase. When the distance and the D/d value was the same, we defined the flatworm entered phase 2. As for phase 3 we defined it when the value was near or equally to 1. Hence, phases 1 was the wandering phase, phase 2 was the phase where the flatworm noticed the vague location of the food, while the third phase was a straight approach. As for the fed flatworm, no movement with recorded, meaning it didn't move (values seen in Table 1).

Figure 2. Screenshot of Video clip of experiment 1 at the beginning and at the end.

A. The screenshot taken at the beginning of the experiment. The cross marks are for distance reference; **B.** The screenshot taken at the end of the experiment. The two black dots in Fig. 2B shows the flatworm before (top: fed) (bottom: starved) The blue line shows the displacement, and the black line shows the distance.

Figure 3. Screenshot of Video clip of experiment 2 at the beginning and at the end.

A. Shows the flatworms taken in the beginning of the experiment. The cross marks the distance reference; **B.** the screenshot taken at the end of the experiment. Shows the flatworms after this experiment with the drawn out map of the route the starved flatworm took and three different phases the flatworm experienced. The blue line mapped out the first phase (the phase which the flatworm wanders around in two circles

around the edge of the petri dish) while the red line mapped out the second phase (the phases where the flatworms noticed the vague location of the pig liver) and the green line mapped out the last phases which the flatworms found the food and move towards it.

4. Discussion

Although it is a common knowledge that when animals are starved, they will find food to eat. Based on our video analysis and also by calculating their eagerness to feed, we found that fed flatworms did not move while starved flatworm is very eager to find food.

Through movement path analysis and the calculate the ratio of distance travelled to displacement (D/d), I found that the starved flatworm could have three different phases of movement. The first phase is the wandering phase when the D/d value is over 2. This phase was observed probably because every single flatworm is confused when put in a petri dish; the second phase is the phase when the flatworm noticed the vague location and is approaching the food source; the third phase is the phase where the flatworm noticed the exact location of the food. The observation of these three phases represented the normal behavior of animals as well as flatworms on how they sense determine and approach food. The normal behavior of animals means, when the animal is starved, the animal will search for food. On the other hand, the fed flatworm did not move at all. This behavior contrasts with the starved flatworm. In conclusion, the starved flatworm is following the normal behavior of animals. On the other hand, fed flatworms did not have the will to search for food.

In summary, we found that starved flatworms were more eager to feed than fed flatworms. In addition, the feeding behavior of starved flatworms could be divided into three different phases. Phase 1 which the flatworm is wandering, phase 2 which the flatworm noticed the vague location of the food and phase 3 where the flatworm moves directly towards the food.

References:

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